

STUDYING FOOD QUALITY AND FUNDAMENTALS OF HEALTHY EATING

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Abstract. *You don't have to be rich to be healthy. Without being rich to be healthy or to be rich is food product quality, lack of knowledge of healthy eating as a result, you may get sick. Good health on earth by 2020, according to the conservation organization 60% of all diseases and 70% of all deaths are non-infectious forms the account of diseases.*

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Relevance. In developed countries it is noted that the disease is more common among the elderly. Today, most of the non-communicable diseases are caused by the heart vascular diseases, diabetes, cancer and the most important of the factors that cause them is incorrect is recognized as eating. The purpose of the topic: As you know, nutrition affects the human body is the most important physiological need. Eating necessary - to cover the energy costs of the organism, cell and continuous creation, updating and functions of textures necessary nutrients for management - proteins, fats, carbohydrates and intake, digestion, absorption and absorption of mineral salts process. Metabolism, all cells, tissues and their activity depend on the nature of the diet. Eating is a complex process, which includes the entry of nutrients into the body, digestion, activities include absorption and absorption. The main nutrients include proteins, fats, hydrogen and organic substances consisting of oxygen compounds, mineral substances, includes vitamins and water. Eating food products is carried out at the expense of Only in the same diseases to the body special nutrients are given: amino acids, vitamins, glucose and others. Food products are natural, rarely artificial Nutrients in the form of compounds are included. Food is eating food consisting of complex mixtures prepared for products. Food ration (food and liquids per day intended amount) – this is a person's intake during a day is the composition and quantity of food products. The absorption of food is its digestion in the digestive tract begins with the release of nutrients into the blood and lymph continues to be absorbed. Nutrients in the body complete with absorption in cells and tissues. The amount of nutrients in food and in the diet the amount of absorption from the total amount (absorption coefficient) is expressed as a percentage. For example, food in a day with the body received 20 mg of iron, and 2 mg from the intestines into the blood absorbed; absorption coefficient of iron is 10 percent constitutes. Coefficient of assimilation of nutrients the specifics of the food included in the diet, the cook of the food to the method of preparation by the digestive organs depends on the situation. Mixed food (animal and plant food) assimilation in the form of food additives). the coefficient of proteins (belkov) averages 84.5%, fats – 94%, carbohydrates (assimilable and non-assimilable total) – 95.6%. All rations and separately considering the nutritional value of food, this is it coefficients are used. Food is food assimilation of substances is indicated above differs from quantities. For example, vegetable carbohydrates absorption coefficient is average - 85%, sugar - 99%. In conclusion, what to eat today Jakhan as a result of scientific research in the field of rationing Protection of public health by health organization Adopt

the principles of healthy eating that are considered necessary are made, these principles are as follows:

1. Eat a variety of food every day
2. Locally several times a day
3. Eat a variety of fresh fruits and vegetables (at least 400g per person per day).
4. Bread and cereal products, cereals, potatoes every day must be consumed.
5. Control the nutrients in the food you eat try to eat plant foods instead of animal foods go through.
6. Low-fat milk and dairy products yogurts and cheeses that are low in fat and salt eat it.
7. Eat less sugar and sugar and contain sugar Choose products with fewer ingredients, sweets and sweets limit the amount of drinks.
8. Do not eat too much salt. Amount of salt per day no more than a teaspoon (5g). Only iodized table salt must be used. Instead of tea, drink natural juices, sugar-free compotes drink boiled water.

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